

**Teaching the Performing Arts for Tomorrow:
A Search for New Perspectives**

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Abstract

Traditionally, the performing art is a visual art which is conceived as those areas of artistic creativity that seek to communicate primarily through the eye and ear. Over the years and in all institutions, the performing arts have always been a medium through which ideas, feelings and meanings are expressed and released through the ingenuity, imaginative impetuses and creativity of an artist. Investigations have revealed that these arts are mostly taught in schools solely by the lecture method activities whereby basic concepts are defined and examples demonstrated in practical terms. Other approaches are not explored. However, it is the opinion of this paper that teaching the performing arts, as an industry, needs to grow beyond this especially in this 21st century of sophistication, experimentation, radicalization, revolution and un-conventionalized methods. Using library and observational methods, this paper examines the methods employed in the teaching of performing arts today and the need for a paradigm shift. The paper concludes that for the performing arts to enjoy the support of both the government, corporate bodies and individuals, new functional teaching approaches occasioned by the introduction of the computer such as power point presentation, the use of smart board, animation technique, graphic design and other visual aids should be embraced. This will enhance teaching and learning and improve their visual perspicacity.

Key words: Teaching, Lecture Method, Performing Arts, New Perspective.

Résumé

Traditionnellement, le théâtre est un art visuel qui est conçu comme certains aspects de la créativité artistique dont l'objectif est de communiquer principalement par le moyen de l'œil et de l'oreille. Au fil des ans et dans toutes les institutions, le théâtre est resté un moyen à travers lequel les idées, les sentiments et les significations sont exprimés et libérés par l'ingéniosité, les impulsions imaginatives et la créativité d'un artiste. Des recherches menées montrent que ces arts sont principalement enseignés dans les écoles uniquement par les méthodes pédagogiques classiques où les concepts de base sont définis avec des exemples pratiques à l'appui. D'autres approches ne sont pas explorées. Voilà pourquoi dans le présent article, nous pensons que l'enseignement du théâtre, en tant qu'industrie, doit se développer au-delà de la complexité du 21^{ème} siècle, caractérisé par l'expérimentation, la radicalisation, la révolution et les méthodes non conventionnelles. Tout en appliquant des méthodes de bibliothèque et d'observation, cet article examine non seulement les méthodes actuellement employées dans l'enseignement du théâtre mais aussi la nécessité d'un changement de méthodes. La conclusion est que le théâtre doit bénéficier du soutien du gouvernement, des entreprises et des individus tout en adoptant des nouvelles approches fonctionnelles d'enseignement par l'ordinateur telles que la présentation PowerPoint, l'utilisation de

tableaux intelligents, la technique d'animation et la conception graphique et d'autres aides visuelles. Cela améliorerait l'enseignement et l'apprentissage ainsi que la perspicacité visuelle dans le théâtre.

Mots-clés: Enseignement, méthode d'enseignement, arts de la scène, nouvelle perspective

Introduction

The performing arts is an offshoot of the word "art", which, in the broadest sense, embraces all the creative discipline such as literature, poetry, drama, music, dance and the visual arts. Indeed, art is a world in itself, a world as round and full and changeable as the world we live in, and like the earth, a whole of many distinct parts. In the words of Jacobs (1997:382), "removing a wedge from the whole and studying it is like touring a country or visiting an era in the past".

The arts are divided into literary, visual and performing arts, but by virtue of their operations and intangible returns, the performing arts, which is the focus of this paper, is more inclined towards visual orientation. These visual arts, including the performing arts are conceived as those areas of artistic creativity and imagination that seek to communicate primarily through the eye. They include: painting, sculpture, architecture, leatherworks, theatre, music, dance, drama and film. But in the context of this discussion, the performing arts will encompass theatre, music dance and film. However, there is the need to further narrow down the scope of this investigation. In furtherance to that, emphasis will be placed on theatre, since it can authoritatively be said to be an umbrella department for dance, music, drama and even film, though, music and film can exist independently. The focus of this paper, therefore, will be manifested in two folds: first to examine the limitations of the teaching methods employed, at present, by teachers, and second, advocate a change of approach especially in this era of technological advancement, radicalization, experimentation and un-conventionalized methods.

The Performing Arts and the Arts of Performance

All through the ages and in all institutions, the performing arts, which among other things, appeal to the aesthetic sense of sight, involve practical work. They are cultivated and learnt. Education, whether formal, informal or semi-formal, plays a very vital role in the process of acquisition of knowledge and skill which makes for practical dexterity. Nwamuo (1996:20) writes that "art education represents the general training, education, development and harmonization of individual's talents in order that they may develop technologically and meaningfully". Education therefore, becomes the bedrock for the development and sustenance of artistic creativity which affects all aspects of the performing arts.

The arts of performance in the performing arts are varied and constitute the engine block with which performances are driven. These arts which include the arts of costume and make-up, stage lighting, scene design, sound engineering and other allied performative elements, are so important that the composite nature of performing arts is achieved when they are all present and brought into a congruous whole. Meanings are usually lost when either of them is conspicuously absent. The mastery of these arts of performance is anchored on proper education by the teacher on the one hand and the students on the other. Moreover,

the intrinsic nature of arts itself and the arts of performance make it necessary that these arts be studied, either as a single entity or as a group in order to enhance effective production of intangible goods and services. Even in the traditional sense before Western education, education has always been part of it. This is summed up by Mbara (2011:33) when he writes that:

... the performing arts tradition, at its developmental processes assumes a graphical dimension with some indigenous forms of artiste-training. It exposes the artistes to the norms of the arts and creates an enabling environment for the development and training of artistes. It also provides ways of tackling the challenges as well as creating an avenue for the study, research and documentation of the performing arts.

Furthermore, because of the divergent nature of the performing/creative arts and the fluidity of art itself, it has necessitated its teaching in both secondary and tertiary institutions in Nigeria. One of the essences is to improve the artistic inclinations of students as well as the expansion of their imaginative impetuses. It is also for these reasons that theatres are built, cultural centres are established and film institutes founded. For instance, sound requires the knowledge of physics and electronics, scene design requires the understanding and mastery of the science of fabrication and joinery among other things. Similarly, the arts of costume and make-up require a good knowledge of textiles, leatherworks and the chemistry of colours. On the other hand, the art of stage lighting, whether natural or artificial, requires full knowledge of, and an understanding of the sciences of colour separation, equipment and tools. Jacob (2011:44-45) captures it succinctly when he writes that:

designers(including light, sound, scenery and props, costume and make-up) are required to be acquainted with the basic principles and theories of electricity, the ohms law... lanterns and lamps.... the usage and functionality of an oscilloscope...., the science of scene design and the importance of and chemistry of colours.

But the questions that should be of utmost concern to us are: has the teaching of performing arts so far been adequate? Do they meet international standards on best practices? Has technology been fully embraced in the teaching of these arts of performance? These and other questions will form the basis of our discussion. However, it has to be pointed out at this juncture that the teaching of the performing arts goes beyond classroom discussions and the teacher and student relationship that exist formally in classes.

Teaching Methods in the Performing Arts

Presently, the methods employed, according to Onwukwe (2005:8), are “solely by the lecture method activities” where basic concepts are defined and elaborated upon. This is

usually done in a class room situation involving the teacher/lecturer and the students. More often than not, examples are given, and in the cases of drama, music and dance, performances are mounted to demonstrate and show in practical terms the nitty-gritty of the course. There is the need for a total overhaul of the methods employed in the teaching of the performing arts in Nigeria today as it has come to be regarded as inadequate in view of the realities on ground. Writing on teaching methodology, Alachi (2008:154) says that:

While the contents have been found adequate, the methods used in passing across these contents have not been too successful as easily observable in the quality and quantity of what our artists have been able to produce during and after graduation from school. The prototype approach being used by our teachers presently cannot meet the yearning desires of this our great nation which is slowly but surely being by-passed by history. There is therefore a need to design a new methodology for teaching the performing arts in our schools. Such methods should not only be practical, creative and innovative but should embrace factors that can transform and translate programmes into practical benefits.

This is the situation on ground today. Efforts are not made to go beyond the pattern described above. This of course, has limitations which hinder the growth and development of the individual and group. Since teachers are catalysts and can stimulate the learner desirous of learning, an ideal teacher therefore, should be ahead of his students in content and emerging methodologies. Corroborating the above with emphasis on “the limits of traditional drama form as a pragmatic change-agent and its failures”, Duruaku (2011:27) pontificates that:

The approach used in presenting a material to a great extent creates appeal or the lack of it. Often the use of varied styles freshen the content of a play by presenting it in various ways and offering perspectives one of which must appeal to an individual, even where he has read, or seen the work earlier.

These teaching methods in the performing arts are increasingly becoming monotonous. Students usually sleep in the class because they are often times not challenged. Cases abound where the majority of students are known to have boycotted a particular lecture because of the teaching method of the lecturer, especially, in the higher institutions where performing arts courses are vigorously pursued. Even when previous performances, documented in CDs are selected and earmarked for practical, one finds out that they are more or less repetitions of an existing concept which adds little or nothing to the mental development of the students.

With these methods on ground, unemployable graduates are produced who may end up constituting nuisance to the society. The spirit to embark on an independent research becomes a herculean task, especially, at the postgraduate level because the individual has

not been exposed to it. Mental development is retarded and the same teaching method may be allowed to flourish especially, if the person finds himself in the teaching profession tomorrow. He may encourage others to explore other variations but cannot do it himself since he was not exposed to it and may not fully utilize it even if it is given to him. Creativity, even when it is innate in the student, becomes stunted, except the student, on his own goes out to develop himself using other learning mechanisms. These limitations cannot easily be wished away without exploring other practical, functional and contemporary teaching methods.

Furthermore, it will be right to put things in clearer perspective concerning the points mentioned above, especially given the fact that some teachers of arts may tend to disagree with my assertions in the area of teaching methods. It is obvious and from investigations that some teachers of arts have gone digital in their teaching methods. But the point we are making is that though the awareness has been created, the level of implementation is poor. For instance, how many teachers of arts presently use power point and smart board in their teaching? Put differently, how many institutions in Nigeria are presently making use of interactive smart board? How many scene designers are familiar with the world of virtual reality and computer generated images (CGI)? The use of visual images is at its low ebb. Yet, some of us boast of our competence and the number of years we have been in the system, as if it is a criterion to know those who are versatile in their teaching approaches. If our students are to improve in their skills, creativity and imaginative impetuses, there is the need for a radicalization of the teaching methods. As earlier stated, alternative approaches that conform to technological wave-lengths presently experienced in the world should be explored.

Alternative Teaching Methods

Teaching and learning enjoy interdependence. In the words of Anyanwu (2002:140), “learning depends on teaching, which in turn, depends on learning.” Therefore, every teaching method has its own implication to learning. Teaching methods all over the world and in all courses have been revolutionized. Performing arts studies in Nigeria cannot be an exception. One of the teaching methods that is capable of enhancing the deeper understanding of the courses in the performing arts is the use of Smart Board. In advanced countries, it is one of the methods in vogue but because of financial constraints and other logistic factors, this teaching method has not fully been implemented and integrated into the Nigerian system. Although markers and white boards are gradually replacing the use of chalk, (in some places, which is a good development) but in this 21st century of sophistication, radicalization and experimentation, the teachers of arts should be familiar with the Smart Board method so as to remain relevant in the profession which not only will help them to improve themselves and their teaching methods, but it will also improve the quality of the students who are learning. With the use of Smart Board, made possible through computer innovation, interaction with the internet while still teaching and evaluation after teaching becomes possible. Variations are also created, and the doses of visual elements in the presentation will help to elicit and sustain interest on the parts of the

students. In other words, visual images are “powerful because they strike at our emotions and our intellect; they move us rather than argue with us” (Uyovbukehri,1985:153). These visual images have the potentialities of achieving change of understanding and stimulate healthy interactions and discussions amongst the students and the lecturers/teachers.

Computer has unlimited dimensions and can be explored and utilized in various ways. Nwachukwu-Agbada (2011:11), in a paper delivered at the 2011 School of Arts conference, Alvan Ikoku Federal College of Education, Owerri says that “since ICT is playing a major function in the teaching and learning contexts in developed countries, and good results are being harnessed out of it, we cannot hide away for too long from using computer and technology.” In that context therefore, another area that computer will help to improve the quality of teaching in the performing arts is through the use of graphic design and computer generated images (CGI). Graphic design which, according to Oladumiye (2002:139), “is concerned with communication of our feelings, ideas, events and experiences with the aim of solving visual problem associated with information, education and entertainment”, is an eye catcher and a universal medium of documenting and communicating ideas. In the same vein, Duruaku (2011:15), in his paper titled “*Nkem efula: Medium Switch for the Preservation and Promulgation of an Igbo folk Heritage*” states that “graphic presentation is easily the most powerful method of mass address asit appeals to the twin senses of vision and sound”. With this technique of generating images which helps to demystify a given subject, meanings are retained and at the same time makes teaching and learning an interesting enterprise and fun.

Experimentation leads to breaking new grounds and sophistication in knowledge. One other area that can be explored and which is capable of adding new knowledge, insight and technique into the teaching of performing arts in Nigeria is the use of animation technique. Though it is an area that is highly demanding because of its technical requirements, it is worth exploring. As far as this writer is concerned, it is still a virgin area that has not been fully explored by the teachers of arts in their teaching methodology. It requires high level of creativity which, according to psychologists, is a combination of flexibility, originality and sensitivity to ideas which enable the thinker to break away from usual sequences of thoughts into different, but satisfying productive sequence. The animation technique emphasizes a general creativity, the ability to think unconventionally, to be innovative, invent and place elements together with a view to enhancing meaningfulness and elevating aesthetic senses and responses. It has become glaringly clear that only pragmatic approaches like the ones mentioned above might present a better alternative to the methods presently used in the teaching of performing arts in Nigeria. Nwadiwe (2008:62) sums it up when he writes that:

The tradition of experimentation particularly in the educational theatre and film should be sustained because of its values in providing new insights and techniques in the concept and practice of theatre and film. The foundation of learning is in the willingness of learners, teachers and practitioners to try new functional approaches of doing things rather than sticking to conventional orthodoxy.

Factors Affecting the Implementation of Alternative Teaching Methods in the Performing Art

One of the problems militating against the effective implementation of these new approaches is the lack of full understanding of the operations, applications and inner workings of these computerized methods. The awareness is there, but the practical application is what is lacking. To some people, it is a mirage and practically impossible. This has affected the growth, development and usage of these new teaching techniques.

In every industry, good, functional equipment along with man power are the key to effective production and turn-over. The performing art is an industry that produces artistic goods and services for human consumption. These goods and services, according to Gondo (2008:1) are “essentially intangible and do not result in the ownership of anything and are not tied to a physical product”. Over the years, artists have struggled to produce these intangible artistic goods and services with what is available since the preferable is usually not available. In most cases, performances and other practical works suffer because of either the use of non-functional tools or the lack of it. As a matter of fact, the state of the Performing Arts Departments in Nigeria has passed an alarming stage. This lack of equipment and tools has generated an intense discussion among scholars and yet, nothing appears to be improving. The Performing Arts are energy sapping enterprise and thrive with creativity, backed up with functional materials. This lack of equipment is a bane to the realization and implementation of these new teaching methods occasioned through the introduction of computer technology.

Inadequate sponsorship or lack of funds is also another factor that affects the implementation of these new teaching methods. The equipment mentioned above are capital intensive. As such, a huge amount of money is required to procure them. For instance, sketches of images drawn in animation format run into thousands of naira. To project them into the film format is a different thing altogether. On the other hand, for a Smart Board to function effectively, it requires a permanently installed projector in the classrooms, which of course, must be air conditioned. This requires huge sums of money.

Lack of constant electricity in Nigeria today militates against the effective operation and implementation of these alternative approaches, especially, the use of smart boards and power point. A smart board is a computerized device that uses a projector, a laptop and an interactive white board. The implication of this is that it can only function when there is power. Unfortunately, this is not the case because the state of power outage in Nigeria has gone from bad to worse to the point that most institutions can stay for weeks without power either from the power generating companies or from the institution’s generating plant. This has made teaching and learning difficult.

The last but not the least is the attitude of some of the teachers of the arts towards these new trends. Some are dogmatic in their views and abhor anything called change. To others, it amounts to unnecessary copying of Western ideas instead of consolidating on the traditional methods already existing. Though we are not subscribing to the total

abandonment of the existing ones, but rather there is the need to be flexible and versatile in one's teaching methods. There should be a healthy blend of the two so as to equip our students with all the necessary skills and knowledge for the world of work.

What do we do?

There is the need for training and retraining of teachers of arts. Nwachukwu-Agbada (2011:14) writes that "were all the teachers to possess PhDs, they would still need to update their skills ... and do some in-service training from time to time." Training here is not basically for talent-hunting but rather the one that is geared towards developing the otherwise dominant productive energies and potentials of an individual which will be beneficial to both himself and the society. In the words of Iji (2001:60):

training "encapsulates the very extended meaning of training and development of the human resources through organized institutions, lectures, workshops, symposia, conferences or teleconferences, among other talk shops for human exchange of ideas and information.

It is the act of increasing the knowledge and skills of an employee for doing a particular job. Since it is a learning process for both the trainers and the trainees, and even the sponsors, it affords them the opportunity to get educated, informed, oriented, reoriented and thereby get intellectually refreshed, enriched towards maximal and optimal utilization of the participants' human potentials. This training has become necessary in view of the present state of affairs in the Performing Arts Industry today. One, it is said, cannot give what one does not have. To this effect, Iji (2001:71) advises that:

the trainers must be on the internet connectivity to enable them assess new trends in the technology of training and human development, and other capacity building technologies or electronics; apart from making copious use of more established communication means such as electronic and print, slides and graphic media.

In a similar development, Olaitan (2013:163) further argues that "skills and methods in teaching can only be acquired, improved upon and enhanced through constant training and development of the educators". Aliyu (2000:7) also corroborates this when he opines that "lack of proper training and retraining of personnel to develop their innate abilities and achieve their full potentials in their places of work will make attainment of standard a mirage".

All the Performing Arts Departments in higher Institutions of learning in Nigeria should be computerized. This is because the alternative teaching methods espoused above can only be feasible and worthwhile when the sophistication brought about by modern technology is explored. Iji (2001:72) affirms this:

It can hardly be over-stressed that every institution; educational, skills acquisition or entrepreneurial organization that fail to imbibe the modern technological and digital culture as an integral part of its current and future operations can hardly survive through the competitive drives this culture has now instituted in the system.

There is also the need to start with few classrooms as demonstration of their possibilities. The advice of Mark Warshauer (in Omorodion, 2002:108) is still relevant today. He opines that:

those who expect to get magnificent results simply from the purchase of expensive and elaborate software will likely be disappointed. But those who put computer software to use in the service of good pedagogy will undoubtedly find ways to enrich their educational program and the learning opportunities of the students.

Nelmes (1999:61) also echoes the above when he says that “... those who successfully manage change have been seen not only to survive but to thrive. Those who ignore change and refuse to respond to it in an appropriate manner will lose out: the technological steamroller will flatten them ...”In the present circumstance, it is particularly a *sine qua non* in training and development. Moreover, in this era of competitive market, it is well-known that computer literacy, programming and other skills and know-how related to information and communication technology have become vitally important as an added advantage for recruitment of fresh employees; a great advantage for promotion for those already on the job, and other performance evaluations in the key aspects of public or private sectors. Graduates of the Performing Arts cannot be found wanting in this regard. It is one thing to procure laptops and send to departments but it is equally another thing to make them functional. It is therefore suggested here that the laptops and other digital devices often distributed to various Departments in many universities be made accessible to the lecturers. They should not be kept in offices as beautification objects but must be practically applied towards performing their functional and utilitarian roles for which they were procured.

Government should declare the Performing Arts Institutions in Nigeria disaster zones by immediately coming to their aid. The Federal Ministry of Education in Nigeria, according to Idolor (2011:10) should “realize that the humanities deserve her attention like any other field of learning; all for a collective stake in the development of the country. This attention should be backed up with an appreciable budget.” Even with the obvious importance of the performing arts, government still treats it abysmally. There is no basis for the undue preference accorded science because according to Schelling as quoted by Sofola (1994:3), “art is the prototype of science; and where art is now, science will come only later ... as an invention”. Obinna (2016:10-11) argues that “there is nothing like science without

arts, and that in every art, there is science – knowledge and the ‘artful’ manner of doing things.” In a similar vein, Ekweariri (2008:85) has opined that “science and technology involve some elements of art in its execution. This is because art involves processes, knowledge and product.” If the energy channelled towards the science by the Federal Government is replicated in the arts, the Performing Arts will be the better for it. The digitalization of the Performing Arts can only work when funds are provided. This paper is of the opinion that government should avoid unnecessary propaganda and match her words with action. This is an era of sophistication and old fashioned approaches of teaching are gradually giving way for un-conventionalized practices. If the Performing Arts are to survive in this global age, government and private individuals should join hands and lift it from this near moribund state.

Teachers of the Performing Arts are encouraged to brace up for this new challenge. Negative attitudes should be jettisoned; especially as it relates to these new teaching methods. Those who are already making use of them in their lectures should encourage others and not boast about it. On the other hand, those who are in the process of learning them should not be envious of those who have already mastered their techniques. They should rather see themselves as partners in progress. This defeatist mentality in some of us should be done away with so as to cultivate the spirit of exploration and research. These new technologically inspired teaching methods are events whose times have come and for the Performing Arts to benefit from them, we must be proactive, dogged, committed and ready to experiment with them.

Conclusion

The Performing Arts, whether they are in the form of drama on stage, music, dance, fine art or film, contribute holistically to the development of our country, Nigeria. The cultural ethos and values embedded in their products cannot be under-estimated. Artistes in all ages have been acclaimed as nation builders and the practical importance of their craft lie in the twin brother of creativity and imagination. According to Sofola (1994:2) in *The Artist and the Tragedy of a Nation*, an artist is “a seer, a visioner, a thinker, a creator, the conscience of the society, a Gadfly, a prophet, a town crier, a teacher, and a revealer of the divine mind”. For the artist to continue to perform these functions enumerated above, the current methods used in teaching them need a total overhaul. In this global age, more is expected of the teachers. Today’s world is ICT driven and the introduction of computer has revolutionized communication and the way people view things. New teaching methods being practised in advanced countries should be replicated here so as to give the students a balanced and an all-inspiring knowledge. Methods such as the use of Smart Board, power point presentation, graphic design, character animation and other approaches as may be introduced by the teacher other than the conventional ones should be vigorously pursued. The world is changing and if the Performing Arts want to remain relevant and produce the right graduates capable of competing favourably with their counterparts elsewhere, it must think digital. However, the success of the implementation of these new methods lies with us as individuals and groups. Therefore, let us join hands together to revolutionize, radicalize and modify our teaching methods through the exploration and experimentation of computer

mediated approaches. This experimentation will lead to sophistication, which in the long run, will improve and enhance teaching and learning.

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Chidiebere: Teaching the Performing Arts for Tomorrow: A Search for New Perspectives

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